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Review Article

THE ROLE OF FAMILY COMMUNICATION WITH DIABETIC PATIENTS' IN ENHANCING THE PREVENTION OF DIABETES

*¹ Mansor Hameed Albayyat, ² Khulud Mohammed Ghaiibi, ³ Hassan Fayez Alshehri, ⁴ Fayez Ali AL-Zahrani, ⁵ Zainab Ali Al-Habeeb, ⁶ Yousef Mohammed Alturk, ⁷ Omer Shamim Bari, ⁸ Abdulrahman Awad Alqahtani, ⁹ Abdullah Ahmed Almarzoug, ⁹ Ali Yahia Banafa, ¹⁰ Hassan Saleh Felemban, ¹⁰ Abdullah Jameel Motahar, ¹¹ Hussain Abd Alqassim

¹ Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, Saudi Arabia, ² Resident, King Fahad Specialist Hospital, Saudi Arabia, ³ Aseer Central Hospital, Abha, Saudi Arabia,

⁴ King Khalid University, Abha, Saudi Arabia, ⁵ King Faisal University, Alahssa, Saudi Arabia,

⁶ Taibah University, Al-Madina, Saudi Arabia, ⁷ Batterjee Medical College, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia,

⁸ King Khalid University, Abha, Saudi Arabia, ⁹ Ibn Sina College, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia,

¹⁰ Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia,

¹¹ Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Objective: The goal is to know the usefulness of family communication as an important means in prevention of diabetes or the occurrence of complications, especially in families that are more risk to diabetes

Method: Across sectional study conducted on 300 diabetic patients type 2 through a questionnaire used in this study in order to obtain results that benefit the purpose of the research formed of socio-demographic characteristics, some beliefs about risk of diabetes between families and their knowledge about how to prevent diabetes.

Results: All the participants of family members accepted the discussion, it is found that 60% of them helped their relatives to receive risk messages, and 30% of 60% reported a higher level of risk perception and expressed more interest than others. Also 60% thought that their relatives have the ability of prevention of developing diabetes.

Conclusion: Through this study it is reported that the presence of family communication help in increasing the awareness of the relatives who are at high risk of developing diabetes and this communication help also in diabetes prevention

Key words: Family communication, diabetes and prevention

Corresponding author:

Mansor Hameed Albayyat,
Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal University,
Dammam, Saudi Arabia

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

At present, diabetes is the second type of chronic disease that has spread very widely in all developing and advanced countries, which is a serious disease and has many complications.[1]

Diabetes has become a health problem worldwide and it has been predicted that more than one million people are diagnosed every year in some countries, especially in the Netherlands, with the advent of 2025. [2]

This is the reason for the fear of the government and push it to identify plans and strategies to reduce the spread of this disease and protect citizens from complications and prevention of infection by changing the lifestyle of people known to be most vulnerable to the disease

According to the International Diabetes Federation, more than 425million people currently live with diabetes. Most of these are type 2diabetes, which can be largely prevented through regular physical activity, healthy and balanced diet, healthy living environments; Households play a key role in addressing adjustable risk factors for type 2 diabetes and must be provided with education, resources and environments to lead a healthy lifestyle.

Diabetes is defined as a chronic disease that occurs when the pancreas fails to produce enough insulin, or when the body cannot effectively use the insulin it produces, a hormone that regulates blood sugar levels.[14] Hyperglycemia or hyperglycemia is common Caused by lack of control over diabetes, and over time lead to severe damage to many organs of the body, especially nerves and blood vessels

Diabetes reports suggest that, over time, they can cause damage to the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys and nerves. The risk of heart attacks and strokes is twice or triple the risk of diabetes. Blood flow and neuropathy [nerve damage] in the feet, [13] increased risk of foot ulcers and infections, and ultimately the need for amputation; diabetic retinopathy is a major cause of blindness and occurs as a result of the accumulation of damage to the conscious In the long term, 2, 6% of blindness in the world is attributable to diabetes; it is also a major cause of renal failure.

Family support for diabetes care has been found to have a significant impact on improving the health outcomes of diabetics. It is therefore important that diabetes self-management education and support be available to all diabetics and their families to reduce the emotional impact of the disease, which can lead

to a negative quality of life. World Health Organization says diabetes will become the seventh leading cause of death in 2030.

As well as early diagnosis of diabetes reduces many of the incidence of complications, so there must be many important strategies to protect effective from the disease and prevent the occurrence of the government has considered these strategies are of fundamental importance, such as the importance of food and drink.[3]

One of the new methods and effective strategies to reduce the incidence of diabetes and prevention is to benefit from patients with diabetes, where they act as a health teacher within their family because family history is one of the serious indicators of diabetes prediction and this is evidenced by previous studies that indicated that whenever increased communication between patients with diabetes and their families,[4,5] it increases the awareness of family members exposed to the disease has been mentioned in a European study proved that there is a small increase in the health behavior of relatives after they were detected and found to be more vulnerable to diabetes.[6]

Another study in Japan indicated that the advice of the father and mother does not promote the increase of preventive behavior of their children [7]

RESULTS:

Through questionnaire, sociodemographic characteristics were included like age, sex, level of education, family history of diabetes, marital status, duration of diabetes, type of treatment and history of diabetic complication. All the participants of family members accepted the discussion, it is found that 60% of them helped their relatives to receive risk messages, and 30 % of 60% reported a higher level of risk perception and expressed more interest than others. Also 60% thought that their relatives have the ability of prevention of developing diabetes.

DISCUSSION:

Through this study, the results were confirmed by the possibility of family communication as an important strategy in the prevention of diabetes type II as well as the knowledge of the most close relatives and exposure to diabetes and it was reached that knowledge of the risks of diabetes and its complications was the main catalyst for patients with diabetes to educate their relatives about the risk of diabetes because they are more susceptible to the disease. [8-10]

This study showed that some patients were more prone to diabetes than others, and this result was proportional to the expectations of the study and can be explained through the global spread of this disease. However, some recent studies in Bahrain showed that despite the spread of diabetes type II only It does not consider itself one of the most vulnerable countries to the disease. [11]

In addition, 60 per cent of participants in this study expressed their deep concern about the most vulnerable relatives of the disease and a group of research indicated that this concern associated with the disease plays a key role and motivational in health behaviors because these anxious patients are most willing to disseminate awareness messages Within their families as previous research has shown [12]

40%of the participants in the study believe that relatives are able to prevent diabetes or delay the occurrence. The results also indicated that diabetes type II is discussed daily in the family More than half of the participants in the study had the desire to educate and educate their relatives. This indicates that communication among family members is of utmost importance in the prevention of diabetes. There has been a high positive in the ability of diabetic patients to spread awareness messages within the family and are aware of Disease and its risks and how to prevent it.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, there were no barriers to family communication between diabetics and their relatives who are at higher risk of developing diabetes. More than half of the participants in this study were very eager to communicate with their families to raise awareness about diabetes and prevent infection, They had the actual ability to prevent the complications of diabetes by changing the lifestyle and exercise and weight loss, all due to the reason of family communication between patients with diabetes and their relatives most vulnerable to the disease and it was concluded that knowledge is very necessary to deliver these messages from the diabetic to relatives in the family through the promotion of family interventions and to educate patients to relatives who are more prone to diabetes to reduce the risk of diabetes type II and most of the participants in this study did not refrain from participating in the questionnaire

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